

TEACHING MATHEMATICS TO BLIND AND VISUALLY IMPAIRED TEENAGERS

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teacher

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Annatation: Most of the study of attitudes to mathematics covered older children and adults. Checking the early development of attitudes towards mathematics is of particular importance for understanding the relationship between them and actual indicators and, if possible, to prevent the development of a strong negative attitude

Keywords: intelligence, development, intuition, perception, attitude

Mathematics is one of the components of education included in the subject "mathematics and computer science". The mathematics course of grades 5-6 consists of the following substantive sections: elements of arithmetic, algebra; elements of geometry; elements of combinatorics. It involves the formation of spatial representations in children, familiarity with the simplest drawing and measuring devices. At the same time, the content contains two additional sections "logic and sets", "mathematics in historical development", which serve the purpose of mastering the elements of a universal mathematical language by students and contribute to the creation of general cultural, humanitarian foundations for studying the course. The course is aimed at forming a mathematical apparatus for solving problems of related topics, including mathematics. Scaling of the system of mathematical knowledge and skills is necessary to understand the rules of installation and use of modern technologies in everyday life, to perceive scientific and technical concepts and ideas, to preach

modeling of phenomena and processes occurring in nature. Mathematics is the science that provides learning. Mathematics The presentation of the main structural elements of cognitive activity in chemistry helps to present the objects of each cycle of kandai, practical skills necessary for making cocktails and professions. The development of ideas about the place of mathematics in the system of sciences contributes to the formation of the qualities of scientific worldview and thinking necessary for adaptation to the modern information space. Requiring students to make mental and volitional efforts, developed imagination, activity, mathematics develops personal qualities: purposefulness, creative activity, independence, responsibility, diligence, critical thinking, the ability to reasonably defend their beliefs. Studying mathematics allows you to form the ability to plan your work, look for rational ways, critically evaluate results, express your thoughts clearly and concisely. All this contributes to the development of communication skills, students and their successful social adaptation, which is especially important for visually impaired and visually impaired schoolchildren. In addition, in the process of studying mathematics, blind and visually impaired children, due to visual defects, should form ideas about what is missing and about the processes taking place in the human world, or the existing ideas should be corrected. In blind and visually impaired children, purposeful work should be carried out to develop the main components of cognitive activity that have their own characteristics, as well as those in need of correction, including mastering special techniques for the study and image of mathematical objects, the formation of visual-sensory analysis skills, the ability to navigate in a small space, visual perception and fine motor skills. development. When implementing the mathematics program for blind and visually impaired students, the goal is set in combination with the goals and objectives of the general education program: creating conditions for meeting the requirements of the state standard of basic general education in mathematics, taking into account the special educational needs of students of this group. Achieving the goal

involves solving the following main tasks:

- creation of correctional and developmental conditions (methodological, technical and hygienic orientation) that contribute to obtaining high-quality mathematical education when teaching mathematics, maximum development of each child's personality, preservation and maintenance of his physical and mental health; social adaptation of children with profound visual impairments;

- correction of developmental defects associated with visual impairments: - formation of the skill of sensory and visual analysis; formation of special techniques for the study and image of the studied objects; 3-formation, refinement, expansion and correction of students' ideas about the subjects and processes of the surrounding reality; - development and correction with the help of mathematics of cognitive activity of students; - develop visual and auditory perception, fine motor skills, spatial representations and the ability to navigate in a small space (in a classroom, notebook, textbook, information provided by a table and graph); - develop monologue speech, form communication skills. Due to the peculiarities of the mathematical material, the need to take into account the age and individual characteristics of students, special educational needs, as well as the need for a differentiated approach in teaching is of great importance. The mathematics program for teaching blind and visually impaired children provides a correctional orientation of learning:

- development of fine motor skills, spatial representations, hand-eye coordination;

- formation of the ability to navigate in a small space;

- development of phonemic hearing, spelling attentiveness, coherent oral and written speech;

- improvement of communication skills, formation of readiness for cooperation, creative activity;

- formation of the ability to communicate, search and find meaningful

compromises;

- develop the ability to recognize similar objects, find similar and distinctive features;

- develop the ability to group items;
- overcoming the inertia of mental processes;
- development of attention at work.

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